

Sum of Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: This paper presents a theorem on the summation of combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computation, combinatorics, binomial coefficient

1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-9]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, a theorem on the summation of combinatorial geometric series is given along with its corollaries.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-9] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Theorem 2. 1: If $x = 1$ in the combinatorial geometric series, then $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r$,

$$i.e. V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1} \Rightarrow V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}.$$

Proof for $V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}$.

$$V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1} \Rightarrow V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}.$$

$$\text{Note that } V_n^r = \frac{(n+r)!}{n! r!}.$$

$$V_n^r + V_{n-1}^{r+1} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n! r!} + \frac{(n-1+r+1)!}{(n-1)! (r+1)!} = (n+r)! \left(\frac{r+1}{n! (r+1)!} + \frac{n}{n! (r+1)!} \right).$$

$$V_n^r + V_{n-1}^{r+1} = (n+r)! \left(\frac{n+r+1}{n!(r+1)!} \right) = \frac{(n+r+1)!}{n!(n+r)!} = V_n^{r+1}.$$

$$\therefore V_n^r + V_{n-1}^{r+1} = V_n^{r+1}.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

Corollary 2.1: $\sum_{i=0}^n 2V_i^r = 2V_n^{r+1}; \sum_{i=0}^n 3V_i^r = 3V_n^{r+1}; \sum_{i=0}^n 3V_i^r = 3V_n^{r+1}; \dots; \sum_{i=0}^n nV_i^r = nV_n^{r+1},$
for $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

Corollary 2.2: $\sum_{i=0}^n xV_i^r = xV_n^{r+1}$, where x is either a real number or complex number.

We know that the partition theorem [5] is: $V_n^r = V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1}$, ($n, r \geq 1$ & $n, r \in N$).

$$\text{Then, } V_n^r + V_{n-1}^{r+1} = V_n^{r+1} \Rightarrow V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1} + V_{n-1}^{r+1} = V_n^{r+1}, (n, r \geq 1 \text{ \& } n, r \in N).$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, a theorem along with its corollaries was constituted on the summation of combinatorial geometric series. This new idea can enable the scientific researchers for research and development further.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2022) Abelian Group on the Binomial Coefficients of Combinatorial Geometric Series. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-mzwxk>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation of Combinatorial Geometric Series and its Combinatorial Identities for Machine Learning and Cybersecurity. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks>.
- [3] Annamalai, C. (2022) Novel Binomial Series and its Summations. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4078523>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2022) Successive Partition Method for Binomial Coefficient in Combinatorial Geometric Series. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7060159>.
- [5] Annamalai, C. (2022) Partition of Multinomial Coefficient. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7063004>.
- [6] Annamalai, C. (2022) A Generalized Method for proving the Theorem derived from the Binomial Coefficients in Combinatorial Geometric Series. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7047548>.

- [7] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and its Applications. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-pnx53-v22>.
- [8] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computing Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Expansion. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4168016>.
- [9] Annamalai, C. (2022) Factorials and Integers for Applications in Computing and Cryptography. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks>.